

Reducing Overhead in Time-Sliced GPU Sharing with Dynamic MPS Partitioning in Kubernetes

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Abstract—Time-slicing GPU resources among multiple workloads in containerized computing environments improves utilization efficiency and lowers costs for machine learning (ML) tasks. Previous research using KubeRay has shown how a ray cluster can fully occupy a GPU when unaccompanied and then seamlessly share it as new workloads arrive. While such time-slicing significantly increases overall GPU usage, frequent context switches among pods can lead to notable overhead and degrade throughput when many pods run simultaneously.

To overcome these challenges, we propose a Kubernetes Operator that injects preconfigured `CUDA_MPS_ACTIVE_THREAD_PERCENTAGE` values into pod specifications using a Kubernetes Admission Webhook, thus enforcing a consistent GPU partitioning policy per node. Our solution leverages the Dynamic Multi-Process Service (MPS) partitioning feature in Nebuly’s GPU scheduler (`nos`), enabling flexible allocation of GPU resources. Under static MPS settings, each pod receives a fixed share of the GPU based on node priority. When all nodes are set to 100% MPS values, `nos` automatically manages partitioning as workloads scale, reducing unnecessary context switches while preserving the low-latency benefits of time-slicing.

Experimental results indicate that our MPS-based approach achieves the lowest total execution time overall, closely matching NVIDIA time-slicing in average per-task performance. By contrast, KubeRay’s time-slicing yields the shortest average execution time but suffers from a longer total runtime, partly due to uneven GPU utilization across different node types. Taken together, these findings demonstrate that a hybrid, operator-driven strategy can effectively strike a balance between fast response times and high-throughput scheduling in shared GPU environments.

Index Terms—GPU sharing, Kubernetes, NVIDIA MPS, resource management, machine learning workloads.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rise of machine learning (ML) and high-performance computing (HPC) has created an urgent need for effective GPU usage in containerized environments. Many existing solutions grant full GPU access to a single container, which often leads to wasted resources when the workload does not fully use the GPU’s capacity. To address this issue, *NVIDIA time-sliced* [1] GPU sharing has become a useful alternative. For instance, *KubeRay* [2] can allocate the entire GPU to a ray clusters and allow workloads to share the GPU resource as they arrive. Although time-slicing clearly raises overall utilization, it also leads to frequent context switches between workloads, causing extra overhead that reduces total throughput—especially when many pods are involved.

To tackle these problems, we introduce a method that use *Multi-Process Service (MPS)* [3]. Our design uses a custom Kubernetes operator that injects predefined `CUDA_MPS_ACTIVE_THREAD_PERCENTAGE` values into pod specifications through a *Kubernetes Admission Webhook*. This webhook intercepts the pod creation process and modifies resource-related fields immediately, ensuring that each pod receives a fixed percentage of GPU capacity on a per-node basis, managed through a priority system. High-priority nodes are given higher MPS percentages (e.g., 100%), while lower-priority nodes receive smaller allocations (e.g., 50%, 33%, or 25%). Meanwhile, Nebuly’s GPU scheduler (`nos`) automatically redistributes execution resources whenever all nodes operate at full capacity, helping balance GPU use as workloads vary. With fewer unnecessary context switches yet preserving the fast response time of time-slicing, our approach aims to boost overall throughput in shared GPU setups.

II. BACKGROUND & RELATED WORK

Several studies have explored the sharing of GPUs to improve resource efficiency. From our previous work [4], demonstrated how time-slicing with KubeRay can successfully distribute ML tasks across multiple pods. Their work showed that while time-slicing significantly increases resource utilization, frequent context switches may reduce overall efficiency, particularly under high concurrency. This finding led to further discussions about the balance between throughput gains and the added overhead of switching between different workloads.

Another related approach is *KubeShare*, introduced by Yeh *et al.* [5]. *KubeShare* treats GPUs as first-class resources within Kubernetes and enables multiple containers to share these devices fairly. By adjusting Kubernetes’ built-in scheduling policies, *KubeShare* aims to provide a consistent method for allocating GPU resources, reducing the risk of individual containers monopolizing the GPU and leaving others starved for compute cycles.

Similarly, Gu *et al.* [6] proposed *FaST-GShare*, a system that uses a custom operator combined with NVIDIA’s exclusive-process mode (`nvidia-smi -c EXCLUSIVE_PROCESS`) and `LD_PRELOAD` to implement fine-grained GPU sharing in serverless (function-as-a-service) settings. This framework allows multiple, short-lived inference requests to run concurrently on the same GPU without suffering substantial

Fig. 1. GPU control layers.

performance penalties, effectively boosting overall resource utilization.

Operators provide a flexible way to extend Kubernetes. According to the Kubebuilder documentation [7], one can define custom controllers that oversee pod creation, dynamic GPU allocations, and other resource policies. In this manner, operators have become a popular strategy for enforcing fine-grained resource governance across a cluster.

Meanwhile, Nebuly’s *nos* [8] An open source device plugin has a dynamic MPS partitioning feature that allows multiple pods to share a GPU concurrently, reducing context-switch overhead. However, this plugin does not provide a built-in mechanism to cap GPU usage at a certain “floor,” potentially allowing one job to dominate whenever additional GPU capacity is available. To address this limitation, we integrate CUDA-level controls via a custom operator. By combining *nos* with our operator, we seek to enforce stricter resource caps while retaining the benefits of dynamic MPS partitioning, thus offering a balanced solution for multi-tenant ML or HPC workloads.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Architecture Design

In this work, as shown in Fig. 1 we leverage Nebuly’s device plugin (NOS) to enable the Multi-Process Service (MPS) daemon on each node in a Kubernetes cluster. By employing Nebuly NOS, we activate the dynamic MPS partitioning feature, thereby allowing fine-grained control over GPU resources at the level of Streaming Multiprocessors (SMs). This approach ensures that multiple containers or pods can concurrently share the same GPU without overhead from context switching.

Additionally, we develop a custom Kubernetes Operator, built using Kubebuilder, that provides a complementary control mechanism at the CUDA level. Specifically, the Operator adjusts the `CUDA_MPS_ACTIVE_THREAD_PERCENTAGE` environment variable in pods that request MPS-based GPU sharing. This environment variable sets a static threshold on the number of active GPU threads a given process may occupy, effectively imposing a per-pod concurrency limit.

```
var nodeConfigs = []NodeConfig{
  {Name: "gsd-ctrlr", Capacity: 1, MPSValue: "100"}, // First priority
  {Name: "gsd-worker1", Capacity: 2, MPSValue: "50"}, // Second priority
  {Name: "gsd-worker2", Capacity: 3, MPSValue: "33"}, // Third priority
  {Name: "gsd-worker3", Capacity: 4, MPSValue: "25"}, // Fourth priority
}
```

Fig. 2. Node Configurations.

B. Node Priority and Capacity

An integral part of our design is the concept of *node priority*, which dictates how pods are scheduled across nodes with varying GPU-sharing configurations. To enforce this, the Operator maintains a predefined list of node configurations, each specifying a node name, capacity (i.e., maximum number of MPS-sharing pods), and an `MPSValue` representing the fraction of GPU threads allocated to each pod on that node. An illustrative configuration as shown in Fig. 2.

This hierarchical setup ensures that nodes with a higher `MPSValue` (e.g., 100%) are filled first. When such high-priority nodes become saturated (i.e., reach their `Capacity` limit), subsequent MPS-sharing pods are placed on the next priority level, which may enforce stricter thread-percentage caps (e.g., 50%, 33%, or 25%). In doing so, our design can *both* maximize performance for higher-priority nodes and accommodate additional workloads on lower-priority nodes, with each node adhering to a specific GPU-sharing policy.

C. Operator Design

The Kubernetes Operator consists of two primary components: (1) a Webhook to mutate pod specifications based on MPS-sharing policies, and (2) a Controller that reconciles pods to ensure their GPU resource requests remain satisfied or rescheduled as needed.

1) Webhook:

- **Label Detection:** The Webhook intercepts all pod creation requests. If a pod is labeled with `mps-share: true`, the Webhook proceeds to inject GPU-sharing configurations.
- **Configuration Injection:** Depending on the desired node selection logic (including node priority), the Mutating Webhook appends or modifies the following fields in the pod specification as shown in Fig. 3.:
 - `nodeSelector`: assigns the node name to which the pod should be scheduled, based on the operator’s node priority list and the current availability.
 - `env`: sets the `CUDA_MPS_ACTIVE_THREAD_PERCENTAGE` according to the node’s configured `MPSValue`.
 - `hostIPC`: set to `true` to enable shared memory segments between the MPS daemon and the container process.
 - `securityContext`: configured to run as user 0 (i.e., root), ensuring that the pod shares the same PID namespace as the MPS daemon.
- **Handling Full Nodes:** If the Webhook detects that a node at a given priority level has reached its capacity (i.e., the

Fig. 3. Webhook Workflow.

maximum number of MPS-sharing pods), it checks the next priority level. If all nodes are fully utilized, the pod is annotated with `no-capacity = true`, forcing it into `Pending` state until capacity becomes available.

- **User-Specified Node:** If the user already specifies a `nodeSelector`, the Webhook verifies whether the chosen node can accommodate additional MPS-sharing pods. If not, it re-labels the pod to `no-capacity = true`, keeping it `Pending`.
- **Node Affinity Checks:** The Webhook respects existing node affinities attached by the user. If a user-provided node affinity conflicts with the MPS capacity or priority settings, the pod is set to `Pending` until resources match or become available.
- **Final Admission:** After all needed fields are injected or updated, the pod configuration is persisted to `etcd`, and the standard Kubernetes scheduler proceeds with the scheduling cycle.

2) Controller:

- **RBAC Permissions:** The Controller operates under Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) rules permitting `get`, `list`, `watch`, `update`, `patch`, and `delete` on pods.
- **Pod Monitoring:** The Controller continuously watches all pods labeled `mps-share = true`.
- **Rescheduling Logic:**
 - If a labeled pod remains in `Pending` state yet a higher-priority node becomes available, the Controller copies the current pod specification and recreates the pod with the suffix `-resched`, thus attempting to schedule it onto the newly freed node.
 - If no suitable node can be found, the Controller continues to reconcile until availability arises.
- **Forced Sharing Requests:** If a user deploys a pod with `--force` and adds the label `mps-share: true` after creation, the Operator still injects the relevant MPS fields and attempts to reschedule if needed.
- **Node Mismatch Handling:**
 - If a pod is configured for standalone GPU usage but is running on a node labeled for MPS sharing, the Controller deletes and recreates the pod with the suffix `-resched` to correct the scheduling mismatch.
 - If the pod is managed by a higher-level Controller (Deployment, ReplicaSet, or DaemonSet), the Oper-

TABLE I
SPECIFICATIONS OF THE MACHINES

Node	CPU	RAM	GPU
gsd-ctrlr	Intel i9-12900K	64 GB	NVIDIA RTX 3090 (24GB)
gsd-worker1	Intel i9-9900K	64 GB	NVIDIA RTX 2080 Ti (12GB)
gsd-worker2	Intel i9-10850K	64 GB	NVIDIA RTX 3090 (24GB)
gsd-worker3	Intel i9-12900K	64 GB	NVIDIA RTX 3090 (12GB)

ator deletes the pod and allows the parent Controller to create a new one, thus aligning with native Kubernetes patterns.

D. Summary of Advantages

By combining Nebuly NOS for dynamic MPS partitioning at the SM (Streaming Multiprocessor) level and the Kubernetes Operator for static CUDA throttling, our design achieves both automated GPU resource balancing and user-defined resource capping. Moreover, by introducing node priority and capacity definitions, we can systematically allocate pods across a tiered structure of MPS values. High-priority nodes yield maximum GPU concurrency, while lower-priority nodes impose stricter concurrency limits to accommodate additional workloads. This hybrid approach can be particularly beneficial in multi-tenant HPC or AI/ML clusters, where dynamic scheduling maximizes overall GPU utilization and static limits help enforce tenant-specific quotas or workload isolation.

IV. EVALUATION

A. Environment Setup

We experimentally conducted on a 4 node Kubernetes cluster including 1 controller node and 3 worker nodes. The specifications for each machine are listed in Table I. All nodes run Ubuntu 22.04.4, with GPU driver version 550.120 and CUDA 12.4 to ensure consistency in computational libraries and drivers across the cluster. A uniform Kubernetes stack underpins the system (Kubernetes 1.31.0, Docker 27.2.0, containerd 1.7.12), the operator under test is developed in Go (version 1.23.4) with Kubebuilder 4.3.1 and managed through Kustomize 5.5.0.

B. Workload

We used a pretrained BERT model for binary text classification to create an inference workload. We assembled a dataset of 200,000 sentences by applying minor synonym changes and optional word shuffling to a smaller group of base sentences. The workload was placed in a container and processed in batches of 1,024 sentences, simulating a realistic inference setting. For each experimental run, the BERT model performed inference on 100 workloads. This setting created a high computational load on the GPU. We recorded and

TABLE II
GPU UTILIZATION OF EACH GPU SHARING METHOD

Approach	NVIDIA 3090 (3 machines)	NVIDIA 2080-Ti
NVIDIA time-slicing	97%	99%
KubeRay with time-slicing	61%	99%
Our Approach	95%	97%

TABLE III
MEMORY UTILIZATION OF EACH GPU SHARING METHOD

Approach	NVIDIA 3090 (3 machines)	NVIDIA 2080-Ti
NVIDIA time-slicing	32.55%	24.89%
KubeRay with time-slicing	20.96%	24.81%
Our Approach	32.31%	24.11%

compared metrics such as total execution time, memory, and GPU utilization for different GPU-sharing setups.

In the following, we describe how we configured each GPU-sharing method:

- NVIDIA time-slicing: Each GPU was split into 4 slices, leading to a total of 16 slices across the 4 nodes. As a result, the system could run up to 16 parallel tasks.
- KubeRay with time-slicing: Each GPU was divided into 4 slices, but each node provided 1 slice to each Ray clusters. In effect, the setup allowed 4 tasks to run in parallel, with each cluster able to distribute its workload across all 4 GPUs.
- MPS Operator (Our Approach): By pairing our custom operator with `nos`, each node could host 4 GPU-bound pods at 100% concurrency, resulting in up to 16 parallel tasks across the entire cluster.

C. Result

This section presents our main findings on GPU utilization, memory usage, and execution time. Table II reports GPU utilization for each method, reflecting resource efficiency. Table III shows GPU memory usage. Table IV summarizes execution times across 100 workloads, including minimum, maximum, average, and total durations.

D. Discussion of GPU Sharing Methods

Each GPU sharing method reveals different benefits and downsides regarding how it uses GPU resources, memory, and execution time. *NVIDIA time-slicing* relies on the default GPU scheduler and achieves consistently high utilization for single processes. However, when multiple tasks share the GPU, it can lead to higher overall execution times due to frequent context switching. From our results, it finishes all workloads in a total time of 1,165 seconds, while its average execution time per workload stands at 169.48 seconds.

In comparison, *KubeRay with time-slicing* splits each set of 25 workloads across four nodes, allowing multiple pods to run in parallel. This arrangement achieves the quickest average completion time (125.68 seconds), making it especially

TABLE IV
WORKLOAD EXECUTION TIME OF EACH GPU SHARING METHOD

Approach	MIN (Sec)	MAX (Sec)	AVG (Sec)	Total (Sec)
NVIDIA time-slicing	82	287	169.48	1,165
KubeRay with time-slicing	89	161	125.68	1,582
Our Approach	66	312	164.58	1,125

attractive for user-facing services that need rapid responses. However, it also leads to the highest total execution time (1,582 seconds), partly because it does not keep certain GPUs fully occupied during the entire process. Another likely reason is that this approach depends on the performance of the slowest GPU in the cluster (the RTX 2080 Ti), causing the more powerful RTX 3090 devices to be underutilized.

Finally, *our MPS Operator* adopts a mix of fixed limits and flexible resource sharing, helping to reduce overhead from context switching. While its average execution time (164.58 seconds) is close to NVIDIA time-slicing, it manages to achieve the lowest total time of 1,125 seconds.

V. CONCLUSION FUTURE WORK

We evaluated three GPU-sharing methods in Kubernetes: NVIDIA time-slicing, KubeRay with time-slicing, and our MPS Operator—each balancing task completion time and throughput differently. KubeRay minimizes average completion time but underutilizes GPUs, while our MPS-based approach achieves the shortest total runtime with minimal impact on task duration.

For future work, we aim to enhance our operator to support both time-slicing and MPS, enabling faster completion of high-priority tasks while maintaining overall throughput, creating a more flexible and efficient resource-sharing framework for ML and HPC workloads.

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